

THE IMAGE OF COLOUR IN THE MIND OF THE NATIVE SPEAKER

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Abstract: *the given article reveals the image of color in the mind of the native speaker, how they gain the color in their mind, their explanation and meaning according to their learning ability.*

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Admittedly, the image of the colour in the mind of native speaker plays a significant role in society and has become a controversial issue in contemporary society. For objects that are what an English speaker would probably describe as white, black, or red, they have specific words too which describe different meaning of the colours. But if we show them just about any other colour, and their language multiplies. By this way we can inform their proper meaning in both context and in the real life of them. "There's a huge amount of variability," says Ted Gibson, a language researcher of foreign country who works with the Tsimane'. "Different people would use different terms for what we would call blue and yellow and orange. They really divide up the space differently, depending on the person."

According to their research, speakers who also speak a lot of Spanish, English, Russian and others say like "yushnus" for blue (-ish) and "shandyes" for green (-ish). But others call both the sky and grass "yushnyes," and others call all green and blue things "shandyes." Or, to take another example, different Tsimane' speakers call yellowish colors "cuchicuciyeisi," "ifuyeisi," or "chamus." In the world of color research, that's unusual to the point of uniqueness. Across languages and cultures, people tend to break up "colorspace," the universe of all the colors humans see, in roughly the same way different words, sure, but for mostly the same colors. So when Gibson told Bevil Conway, a vision researcher at the National Institutes of Health's Intramural Research Program, about his findings with the Tsimane', Conway wanted to know more.

Conway studies color and vision; Gibson studies language and information theory, and had been looking at the way Tsimane' speakers use numbers. Together, they cooked up a new research project to figure out how Tsimane' speakers see what they see or, more accurately, how they talk about what they see. Because if you accept that all humans with normal vision are capable of seeing the same vast range of colors (which they are) but vary in the way they *talk* about those colors (which they do), that says something about how they think. Color turns out to be a very good vector for figuring out how the human brain actually works. So

the hypothesis was that maybe something about those colors, or the human brain's perception of those colors, is more fundamental than culture like, the human brain has a "deep grammar" for color, a hard-coded categorization of the color space.

In general, Uzbek and Russian are pretty sophisticated about communicating color. Tsimane', as Gibson had explained to Conway at their first lunch together, doesn't have as many color words and doesn't use them as precisely. "But the kind of surprising conclusion was that these three languages, even though they're totally different, have pretty much the same pattern when you rank-order the chips by their communicative efficiency," Conway says.

In other words: An English speaker and a Tsimane' speaker have roughly the same difficulty conveying the same colors. Munsell color chips rank-ordered left-to-right by how effectively the color chip is communicated. Each row shows data for a given language. The rows are ordered according to the overall communication efficiency of each language.

While colors don't vary much from biome to biome, the colors of the built environment do. Nobody would confuse Hong Kong's lite-brite nighttime cityscape with a crystalline autumn morning in Boston. "One of the great advances of industrialization is the expansion of the gamut. We're now at the point where we have HD color televisions capable of producing many more saturated colors than we've ever been able to produce," Conway says. "The earliest cave artists had two kinds of ochres and charcoal. This radical change to our environments that we brought about is the addition of synthetic pigments."

It won't be easy to test the hypothesis; people study color not just because it's a fascinating way to get into someone else's head is your red the same as my red? but because it digs into how the machinery of human perception and cognition. Somehow, with nothing more than eyes, retinas, and a hefty tangle of neurons, people build entire, colorful worlds in their heads. "We just don't understand enough about how high-level color vision is done by the brain," Lindsay says. What we talk about when we talk about color is nothing less than the human brain making the cognitive world.

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